

Controlling sheath rot (ShR) in rice

H.D. Lewin and P. Vidhyasekaran, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

All the high yielding cultivars in Tamil Nadu are susceptible to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* Sawada. The disease is severe during samba and thaladi seasons (Aug-Feb).

Several fungicides inhibited mycelial growth of the fungus *in vitro*. Their efficacy in the field was tested with cultivar Co 43 in four annual trials 1982-86. Plot size was 24 m² in a randomized block design with 4 replications. The fungicides were sprayed at panicle initiation and 15 d later. Disease intensity was assessed 10 d before harvest.

All fungicides tested — carbendazim (0.1%), edifenphos (0.1%), mancozeb (0.25%), thiophanate methyl (0.1%), captafol (0.125%), carboxin (0.2%), glycofene (0.2%), validamycin (0.1%), IBP (0.1%), iprodione (0.1%), tridemorph (0.1%), and copper oxychloride (0.25%) — were ineffective. □

Pseudomonas fluorescens suppresses development of bacterial blight (BB) symptoms

C.S. Anuratha and S.S. Gnanamanickam, Centre for Advanced Studies in Botany, Guindy, University of Madras, Madras 600025, India

Xanthomonas campestris pv. *oryzae*, the BB pathogen, was isolated from naturally infected IR20 and ADT36 plants collected from Coimbatore and Tirurkuppam fields. We also isolated native strains of *P. fluorescens* (biotype III) from roots of rice, pearl millet, and citrus.

In *in vitro* assays, all *P. fluorescens* strains restricted the growth of *X. c.* pv. *oryzae*. The strain isolated from rice inhibited growth the most. The diameter of inhibition zones varied

from 1.1 to 5.1 cm. The citrus strain was used in greenhouse experiments. Bacteria-coated rice seeds and nontreated seeds were planted in pots.

P. fluorescens (10⁸ cfu/ml) was mixed with a 1% solution of sterile carboxy methyl cellulose and powdered vermiculite, and dried overnight at room temperature (28°C). Control seeds were coated with a mixture that did not contain the bacteria. Bacterized seedlings received a spray with *P. fluorescens* (10⁸ cfu/ml) 20 d after seeding. Four hours later, bacterized and nonbacterized seedlings were inoculated with *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* (10⁶ cfu/ml) by the standard clipping technique. The seedlings were maintained on greenhouse benches (24-25 °C). Severity of BB was recorded 7 d after inoculation.

Bacterized rice plants showed substantial reduction (40-60%) in BB severity (see table). □

Effect of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* treatment on BB incidence in rice, Madras, India.^a

Cultivar	Treatment	BB index ^b in 3 experiments		
		I	II	III
TN1	Untreated	3.6	5.6	6.3
	Treated	1.9	3.0	3.8
	Difference	1.7**	2.6**	2.5**
IR8	Untreated	3.4	7.2	—
	Treated	2.0	3.3	—
	Difference	1.4*	3.9**	—
TKM9	Untreated	1.6	—	—
	Treated	3.0	—	—
	Difference	4.6**	—	—

^aAv of 60-187 observations each. ^b't' value significant at P = 0.05 (*) and P = 0.01 (**).

Multiplication and movement of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in the rice plant

P.R. Ray and J.N. Chand, Plant Pathology Department, HAU, Hisar, India; and S. S. Malik, HAU, Rice Research Station, Kaul 132021, India

Multiplication of the BB pathogen in host tissue would be reflected in the total inoculum generated and scope for further disease buildup and spread.

Seed of resistant IET4141 and susceptible TN1 were sown separately in earthen pots during Jul-Aug 1985. Seedlings were thinned to five uniformly spaced plants per pot.

Plants were inoculated at 6 wk with bacterial suspension (OD 1 at 600 nm) using the clipping technique. Lesion lengths were measured in 10 leaves of each variety at 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 d after inoculation.

One-square-centimeter sample leaf areas from the tip of inoculated leaves collected at intervals up to 12 d were assessed for *in vivo* multiplication. Each leaf piece was macerated aseptically in a mortar and pestle and a tenfold dilution was plated on NDA in triplicated petri plates. The petri plates were incubated at 27-30°C and colonies were counted after 48 h. Two leaf pieces were used for each variety at each interval.

The *in vivo* multiplication of the bacterium and population buildup per unit area of inoculated leaves at different intervals were faster in the susceptible variety than in the resistant variety (see table). Lesions developed in the susceptible variety when the population level reached 10³ at 3 d and expanded rapidly to a maximum of 15 cm at 15 d. In the resistant variety, lesions developed at 9 d after inoculation when the population level reached about 10⁶ and expanded gradually to a maximum of 3.5 cm at 15 d. The bacterium population declined faster in the lesions of the susceptible variety than in the resistant variety. Most of the lesion area in both